

Interview Jean-Francois Leclerc - Aeroscope Atlantique
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution

Aeroscope Atlantique (AA) was created in 1993 to federate several local associations interested in the preservation of the aeronautical heritage, with the purpose to establish themselves as a cultural center, not a museum.

The cultural center is called "Le Grenier de l'Aviation". From 2012 to 2019, it was located in St-Herblain. Since 2021, the association has a new address and exhibition space, in Bouguennais. (Both towns located near Nantes).

1 of the members of AA is another association: l'Amicale du Super Constellation (ASC), which preserves one of the only existing examples of this very famous American aircraft (designed just before WWII, put into service after the war for passenger transport, this one belonged to Air France). The aircraft arrived in Nantes in 1974. It is property of the French state and listed as Historical Monument. ASC ensures the maintenance and restoration of the aircraft.

This aircraft is currently located in a field belonging to a local farmer, near Nantes airport. The priority for future project is to shelter it.

Other members of AA : most of the other former associations have disappeared. Today mainly individual members in addition to the Amicale du Super Constellation.

One of the members of ASC is the president of the association aiming to recover the Focke Wulf aircraft out of Lac de Grand Lieu.

Jean-Francois Leclerc (JFL) is the President of AA. He is a sculptor himself, also worked as an engineer in aeronautics. He is now retired.

AA collections are related to aeronautics in general, from air balloons to recent aircrafts. They include aircrafts, engines, models, but also uniforms, archives (paper, video), documentation.

Exhibition on the life of Jacqueline Auriol, who lived in St-Herblain.

Exhibition on sculptures and amateur airplane constructions, such as the RL21 built by Rene Le Duc (listed as historical monument), conceived in a process close to that of a sculptor.

Exhibition of photos paralleling birds' attitudes in flight and planes.

AA also displays remains from WWII, exhibition of pieces on loan from other associations such as ABSA 39-45 (e.g., a Messerschmitt aircraft including a dummy of the pilot in his flight suit).

Exhibition space in St-Herblain : 1600 m2 located in a shopping center; premisses not suited to receive the public.

Exhibition space was very loaded, with 12 planes and 2 gliders (including a German glider recovered as war damage)

- The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved ? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing ? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects ?

AA does a lot of historical and archival research, but they are not involved in excavations/recoveries of wrecks.

AA has 2 parts of a plane shot down about 20km from Nantes. These parts have been donated to the association in the past, by the farmer in whose field they were located. But JFL is not sure how the process took place. The pieces were damaged in a fire in a military hangar. See fiche A, on loan to Arc Antique.

Integrating new artefacts : according to their relevance to the subject of history of aeronautics. AA seeks to be able to tell everyday stories about what happened in relation to the pieces collected. AA's primary focus is local history (around Nantes) but remains open to wider perspectives. Super Constellation has become a local story.

JFL would like to bring a wider audience to appreciate aeronautical heritage.

AA has permanent presentations and temporary exhibitions, various artefacts in their collections are on display according to the topics addressed in the exhibitions.

AA also exhibit pieces from other associations.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage ? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations ? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution ?

A question that was never asked as such before the Procraft project, except perhaps for the Super Constellation in relation to outdoor storage.

No awareness before concerning conservation needs of the various materials.

JFL understands the need to better control conservation conditions in the same way as fine art collections. Conservation will become a more prominent subject, but a question of means is fundamental.

JFL considers long-term to cover several hundred years for this type of heritage, very recent.

He is also considers the possibility to present parts/aircraft in different conditions and appearances, from archaeological to refurbished state, complete or incomplete, as long as there is a (human) story behind it.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery) : conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly ? (addition to Form A)

AA does not do too much restoration on WWII parts. The main restoration operations are carried out on the Super Constellation.

Super Constellation : completely stripped to bare metal and repainted in the colors of Air France in the 50's. Cockpit restoration, sealing to make it watertight.
Financial help from the DRAC, but must advance the funds.

RL 21 : Polishing with cotton wool for polishing Al.

Background for association members : most of the members have wanted to be part of the aviation world, they compensate unfulfilled passion in their retirement. Former Air Force member as a mechanic. There are also people completely foreign to the aeronautical field, e.g., 1 documentalist. Some are also experts, e.g., aircraft mechanics, pilots.

Team on Super Constellation: the project manager is not from aeronautics, he is a former worksite manager for EDF. Team guided by external skills and professionals, who are happy to help with the project.

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact : aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage /outdoors (addition to Form A) ?

WWII related artefacts: only the two pieces communicated to Arc Antique. Rest in the exhibition came from loans from other associations or private owners.

Choice of exhibition according to the subject.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage) : rooms or hall ? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A) ?

The new premises are an old garage and a former workshop of a professional painter. It includes 2 offices and common areas.

It is not sure to be able to heat. The most fragile models.

Aircraft which did not belong to AA have been returned to the owners. Other aircraft owned by the association are on deposit in the Angers and Vannes museums until the new exhibition space is ready for displaying them again.

New storage place near the airport : faces south-west, wind from the sea going towards Nantes.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems) ? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks ? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

Pieces are covered with a whitish layer which alters the appearance.

Polishing to restore a shiny appearance: with cotton wool and motorcycle polishing products. Not too often so as not to lose material.

But JFL and association members in general don't really know how to determine the exact issue, whether it is corrosion or surface tarnishing.

- Reflecting on their own practice : do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts ? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about ? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field ? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

Awareness about certain needs with Procraft project, e.g., build a shelter for Super Constellation. But they are not necessarily a priority in future project for a museum.

The Super Constellation is a delicate subject, the association is afraid of loosing it. They have heard that the state would like to transfer it to the Musée de l'Air et de l'Espace at Le Bourget. JFL is worried about this aircraft being forgotten if goes to another place or museum.

Another delicate subject is what is to become of the artefacts coming from illegal excavations : this is the case of the pieces that the association has. Today they know better what to do or not about archaeological finds/recoveries.

Regular relations with different bodies, friendship connections; members of a museum near Angers (Espace Air Passion). Association have resumed their connection with Vannes, to resolve certain legal aspects of the loan they have there.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history ?

As long as there is a story to tell, that's what counts. No particular focus on WWII period.